

IP4OS

Survey protocol: exploring best practices in intellectual property (IP) and open science (OS)

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Table of contents

1. Summary	4
2. List of abbreviations	4
3. Purpose and significance	5
4. Study design	5
4.1. Survey administration and platform	5
4.2. Target participants and recruitment strategy	6
4.3. Optional follow-up interviews	7
5. Data Collection and Analysis	7
5.1. Data Collection Process	7
5.2. Data Analysis Approach	7
6. Ethical Considerations	7
7. Expected Outcomes and Impact	8

1. Summary

This protocol outlines the methodology for conducting a survey aimed at identifying current and best practices in integrating Intellectual Property (IP) management with Open Science (OS) principles within the Research & Innovation (R&I) ecosystem. The survey will gather stakeholder perspectives from multiple sectors, including academia, industry, legal entities, and policymaking bodies, to assess existing challenges, opportunities and successful approaches in balancing openness with IP protection. Another aspect is the exploration of policy and institutional strategies that facilitate the responsible use of IP while promoting the principles of OS. The study will employ a structured questionnaire with both closed-ended and open-ended questions, administered via the secure REDCap platform. Recruitment will target diverse professional groups engaged in IP and OS, ensuring broad representation of the stakeholder perspectives mentioned above. The survey will remain open for several weeks, with reminder emails sent to enhance response rates. Optional follow-up interviews will be conducted with selected participants who provide particularly insightful responses. These interviews will explore case studies and recommendations in greater depth. Collected data will be analysed using a mixed-methods approach, combining statistical analysis of quantitative responses with thematic coding of qualitative feedback. The study adheres to ethical research standards, ensuring informed consent, anonymity, and compliance with data protection regulations. Findings will inform the Synergy Framework and will also be used in elaborating policy briefs, academic publications, and training materials, contributing to evidence-based policymaking and institutional strategies for optimising IP and OS integration.

2. List of abbreviations

IP Intellectual Property

OS Open Science

R&I Research & Innovation

RFOs Research Funding Organisations

RPOs Research Performing Organisations

KTT Knowledge and Technology Transfer

SMEs Small and Medium-sized Enterprises

EU European Union

GDPR General Data Protection Regulation

REDCap Research Electronic Data Capture

3. Purpose and significance

Intellectual Property (IP) and Open Science (OS) are often described as conflicting concepts in the global research and innovation ecosystem. IP and more specifically, measures to protect and transfer Intellectual Property Rights (IPRs) such as patents, trademarks, copyright, designs and more, is connected to valorisation and commercialisation of research. It provides inventors and inventions owners with the legal rights to control the (re-)use of their discoveries, thereby supporting innovation through exclusivity. It is often perceived, reductively, as being about closing access to research results, obliging users to seek permissions and/or pay licences before making use of assets. OS, on the other hand, is often described as a principle that prioritises accessibility, reproducibility and transparency in knowledge dissemination, advocating for publicly available research outputs, data, and methodologies.

The increasing emphasis on research-led innovation, open access, data-sharing policies, and open-source technologies has brought attention to the intersection of these typical IP and OS descriptions, making it crucial to explore and reevaluate understandings and approaches. This work aims to identify IP management approaches that support the promotion of OS while maximizing the value generated from research, ultimately leading to the optimal use and valorisation of research knowledge.

The challenge lies in emphasising the potential complementarities between these two concepts, and how to achieve this. Institutions, policymakers, and industries must navigate this dynamic space to strengthen the valorisation of private and public knowledge for society, economy as well as to master the green and digital transitions.

However, there is a lack of comprehensive understanding regarding the best practices that integrate IP and OS in the Research & Innovation (R&I) eco-system without hindering scientific progress or economic incentives.

This survey aims to identify and analyse best practices for the design of IP management strategies that are consistent with the pursuit of OS across multiple sectors, including academia, industry, legal entities, and policymaking bodies. By exploring stakeholder perspectives, experiences, and challenges through this survey's results, we will provide actionable recommendations to improve training and recommend policies, frameworks, and institutional strategies that facilitate both appropriate IP management and OS practices. The survey results are particularly relevant in the context of emerging trends such as open data mandates, collaborative research initiatives, and knowledge transfer models that emphasise both commercialisation and knowledge sharing. The findings will support the development of a high-quality training concept, inform evidence-based policymaking and guide institutions in formulating robust strategies to integrate IP and OS principles fostering an innovative and competitive Europe.

4. Study design

This survey combines both closed-ended and open-ended questions to capture a comprehensive understanding of stakeholder perspectives. Closed-ended questions will enable the quantification of trends, attitudes, and levels of awareness regarding IP and OS interactions, while open-ended questions will allow respondents to elaborate on specific experiences, challenges, and practices to derive recommendations for a concerted IP-OS practice.

4.1. Survey administration and platform

The survey will be administered using Research Electronic Data Capture (REDCap), a secure, web-based application designed for survey research. REDCap ensures data

security, user anonymity, and efficient data management, making it an ideal platform for conducting research with multiple stakeholder groups. The survey will be structured to take approximately 10–12 minutes to complete, ensuring that respondents can provide thoughtful responses without experiencing survey fatigue.

4.2. Target participants and recruitment strategy

To gain diverse insights, the study will engage multiple stakeholder groups who interact with IP and OS frameworks in their respective fields. These include:

- **KTTP Professionals** who facilitate the transfer of knowledge and technology between research institutions and industry.
- **Infrastructure-providing stakeholders in the EU R&I system**, including Research Funding Organisations (RFOs), Research Performing Organisations (RPOs), publishers, and companies involved in science communication and dissemination within EU projects.
- **Entrepreneurship Officers**, supporting innovation and business development within academic and research environments.
- **Research Librarians** and **Teaching Librarians**, who manage access to scholarly resources and support open science initiatives.
- **Data Managers / Data Stewards**, ensuring responsible data management and compliance with open data policies.
- **Research Managers**, who oversee the administration and strategic planning of research activities.
- **Policymakers**, who act as promoters and supporters of scientific messages and tools, shaping national and institutional frameworks for IP and OS.
- **OS Ambassadors**, advocating for open science principles and best practices.
- **Researchers** and **Research Students** contributing to scientific advancements..
- **Academic and University Lecturers** influencing research practices and integrating OS principles into education.
- **Innovation Managers in Industry & SMEs**, particularly those collaborating with the public sector on open innovation and IP management.
- **RPO's Professional, Managerial, and/or Academic Staff**, involved in implementing and supporting research and innovation policies.
- **Innovators from Spin-Offs and Start-Ups**, developing and commercialising research-driven innovations.
- **Citizen Science Representatives**, fostering public engagement in scientific research and encouraging collaboration between professional researchers and non-expert contributors.
- **Legal Experts**, providing legal guidance on intellectual property rights, patenting strategies, and compliance with IP regulations in research and innovation.

The survey participants will be recruited through targeted outreach efforts, including professional networks of project members, institutional mailing lists, industry consortia, and social media platforms. Collaborations with universities, research institutions, knowledge and technology transfer offices, IP offices, innovation clusters, and professional associations will help ensure broad representation across different stakeholder groups. To mitigate selection bias, recruitment efforts will focus on engaging a diverse range of respondents rather than concentrating responses from any single sector.

The survey will remain accessible for an extended period to maximise response rates and ensure the collection of a sufficient number of responses for a rigorous analysis. During this timeframe, two reminder emails will be disseminated to enhance participant engagement

and mitigate non-response bias. This approach balances the need for comprehensive data collection with adherence to the study's timeline and methodological rigour.

4.3. Optional follow-up interviews

To gain deeper insights into key findings from the survey, respondents will have the option to participate in a follow-up online interview. The interview phase will not be open to all survey participants but will focus on those whose responses indicate particularly insightful perspectives that warrant further exploration. If these respondents have voluntarily provided their email addresses, they may be contacted for follow-up interviews. Selection will ensure a broad representation of perspectives, including IP to OS, to capture diverse viewpoints. These interviews will focus on exploring specific challenges, case studies, and recommendations for improving the integration of IP and OS practices. Interview data will complement survey findings, providing rich qualitative insights into how stakeholders face the complexities of IP-OS interactions. We may also be in contact with institutions with particularly positive experiences subsequently in the project, although such participation will be optional.

5. Data Collection and Analysis

5.1. Data Collection Process

The survey will be distributed electronically via REDCap using a secure and dedicated link. Prior to participation, respondents will be presented with clear information regarding the purpose of the study, data protection measures, and the voluntary nature of their involvement. Informed consent is implied by the respondent's decision to proceed with the survey and participation may be discontinued at any point without consequence. Given the sensitivity of IP-related discussions, responses will remain completely anonymous, with no personally identifiable information collected other than email (if the respondent agrees to provide). The study will also comply with data protection regulations to maintain participant confidentiality.

5.2. Data Analysis Approach

Data analysis will follow a mixed-methods approach to extract meaningful insights from both quantitative and qualitative responses.

Quantitative Analysis (Closed-Ended Responses)

- Descriptive statistics will be used to summarise key trends, including the distribution of stakeholder opinions, familiarity with IP and OS principles, and perceived challenges in balancing the two frameworks.
- Cross-tabulations will be performed to compare responses across different stakeholder groups (e.g., industry vs. academia, policymakers vs. researchers).

Qualitative Analysis (Open-Ended Responses)

- Thematic coding will be employed to identify recurring themes, narratives, and perspectives emerging from open-ended survey responses.
- Pattern recognition will help highlight key insights, such as common concerns about IP restrictions, experiences with open-access publishing, and successful models of IP-OS collaboration.
- Content analysis will allow for categorisation of responses into broader thematic clusters, supporting the development of evidence-based recommendations.

6. Ethical Considerations

This survey and subsequent data handling will adhere to ethical research principles, ensuring informed consent, anonymity, and voluntary participation. Participants will be provided with detailed study information before taking the survey, outlining the research objectives, data usage, and confidentiality measures. No sensitive personal data will be collected, and respondents can withdraw at any time without consequences. The research team will follow the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and other relevant data protection laws to ensure the confidentiality and security of collected data. Given that the survey does not seek directly identifiable personal data beyond general demographic information, such as affiliation and country, the project partners collectively decided in a project meeting that a formal ethics review was not necessary for this study. While participants will provide their affiliating organisation and may also choose to provide their institutional/professional email addresses for potential follow-up, these will be stored securely and separately from survey responses to maintain confidentiality. They will be used solely for the stated purpose and will not be shared with third parties. Affiliation data will not be used for individual analysis but will serve to contextualise best practices across different organisational types and sectors. It will be aggregated to understand trends at an institutional/country level without linking responses to specific individuals.

7. Expected Outcomes and Impact

The study is expected to gather valuable insights into the current state of IP and OS integration, identifying best practices, challenges, and opportunities for improvement. By analysing stakeholder perspectives, this survey will contribute to:

- Developing strategies to balance IP protection with OS principles.
- Guiding institutions and policymakers in crafting policies that encourage both innovation and open knowledge-sharing.
- Enhancing collaboration between academia, industry, legal professionals, and policymakers to create sustainable IP-OS frameworks.
- Informing funding agencies on best practices for structuring research grants and open-access policies.

The findings will be disseminated through a research report, training, policy briefs, academic publications, and stakeholder workshops, ensuring that the insights reach decision-makers and practitioners who can implement evidence-based solutions. As highlighted above, we may also seek to follow up with institutions with particularly valuable experiences subsequently in the project. Such engagement will be entirely optional.